

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED MoSi_2 -BASED COMPOSITES

A.R. Bhatti and R.A. Shatwell

Structural Materials Centre, DRA Farnborough, Hampshire, GU14 6TD, UK.

SUMMARY: High density continuous reinforced MoSi_2 -based composites have been produced by hot-pressing technique. Both SiC and single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre reinforcements were investigated. Modification of MoSi_2 matrix with sialon powder minimises the thermal expansion mismatch with the SiC fibre, thereby suppressing the matrix cracking. No matrix cracking was observed in Al_2O_3 reinforced MoSi_2 composites due to good fibre/matrix thermal expansion match.

Microstructural and EDS studies of interfacial regions in SiC reinforced MoSi_2 /Sialon and single crystal Al_2O_3 reinforced MoSi_2 composites have identified the formation of Mo_5Si_3 and mullite phases respectively. Key issues concerning these reaction phases and their influence on the mechanical properties are presented.

KEYWORDS: MoSi_2 , matrix cracking, continuous fibre reinforcement, thermal expansion, fibre/matrix interface, sialon, mullite, scanning electron microscopy

INTRODUCTION

Molybdenum disilicide (MoSi_2) based composites are very attractive candidates for various high temperature aerospace and industrial applications. MoSi_2 has high melting point of 2030°C , excellent oxidation resistance and good thermal and electrical conductivity [1,2]. Additionally it can be electro-discharge machined which is a significant advantage for the low cost fabrication of components. Mechanically, it exhibits a brittle-to-ductile transition at $\sim 1000^\circ\text{C}$. Creep effects could reduce its high temperature strength.

Several attempts have been made to increase both the low temperature toughness and the high temperature creep resistance of MoSi_2 . Recent work on the addition of SiC powder and whiskers to MoSi_2 [3,4], has shown small improvements both in fracture toughness and high temperature resistance. ZrO_2 additions also improve room temperature fracture toughness [5]. Both strength and creep resistance are improved by alloying MoSi_2 with WSi_2 [6]. Substantial improvements are necessary to achieve the required levels of damage tolerance and strength for high temperature engineering applications. Reinforcing MoSi_2 with continuous fibres could achieve substantial improvements in mechanical properties. The use of refractory metal fibres such as Nb and Ta into MoSi_2 matrix has demonstrated significant improvements in toughness [7,8]. However, this type of fibres react with the matrix at high temperatures which leads to the formation of trisilicides $(\text{Mo,Nb})_5\text{Si}_3$ and $(\text{Mo,Ta})_5\text{Si}_3$ at the interface between MoSi_2 and the refractory metal fibre. Additional reaction barrier coatings are, therefore, necessary in order to minimise reaction effects [9].

In previous study, the use of SiC based, Textron SCS-6 SiC reinforcement to MoSi₂ matrix was investigated [10]. The material showed extensive matrix cracking which occurred during its high temperature processing. This cracking was attributed to the large thermal expansion mismatch between the SCS-6 SiC fibre ($4.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) and the MoSi₂ matrix ($7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$).

In this paper, the results of an approach, whereby the composition of the matrix is modified by the addition of sialon powder to reduce the thermal expansion mismatch between the SiC fibre and the matrix, are presented. The work was extended to incorporate Saphikon single crystal Al₂O₃ fibre with thermal expansion $\sim 8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, a reasonably close match to that of MoSi₂ matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fabrication of Composite Materials

Starting materials were MoSi₂ powder (Starck, Grade C) and Sialon (Vesuvius Zyalons, 101). The fibres used were Textron, SCS-6 and Saphikon single crystal Al₂O₃. The SCS-6 SiC fibre essentially consists of a SiC sheath with an outer diameter of $\sim 140 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ surrounding a carbon core with a diameter of $\sim 33 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The outer surface of the SiC sheath has a carbon rich coating approximately $3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick. The Saphikon single crystal Al₂O₃ has a diameter $\sim 125 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

MoSi₂ and Sialon powders were blended by ball milling. A composite with 10 vol% SCS-6 SiC fibre), reinforcing a matrix, comprising of 60 vol% MoSi₂ and 40 vol% Sialon was prepared via a three stage route. A SiC fibre was wound onto a drum and coated with a slurry, consisting of the blended ceramic powders and dispersants with a polymer binder in an alcohol solvent. The sheet was removed from the drum and dried. Coupons were punched out of the dried sheet and stacked to produce the green composite. This was heated to remove the the binder. The compact was coated with BN and then hot pressed in atmosphere in a graphite die at 1650°C under 18MPa for 1 hour. The pressure was applied using two close fitting graphite plungers in a hydraulic press. The heating was applied by radio frequency induction using a Radyne 150E generator. The composite had density $>99\%$ of theoretical. The hot pressed blocks were rectangular measuring typically $45\text{mm} \times 25\text{mm} \times 8\text{mm}$ in size.

Single crystal Al₂O₃ fibre reinforced MoSi₂ matrix composites were prepared using 100% MoSi₂ powder. The fabrication route was essentially the same as used for SCS-6 SiC reinforced MoSi₂/Sialon composites. A slurry consisting of MoSi₂ and dispersants with a polymer binder in an alcohol solvent was prepared and cast onto the wound up fibres. After drying, sheets were punched out, laid up to produce the green composite compact, pressed and heated to remove the binder. The composite was then hot pressed as before. Two blocks of composites, with 16 and 20 vol% fibre, were produced. Both the composite blocks had density close to theoretical density.

Microstructural examination

The composites were examined by optical metallography, X-ray diffractometry (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) with EDS system. SEM was performed both in secondary and backscattered electron imaging modes. Samples for TEM observation were pre-coated with Au.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure of SiC fibre reinforced MoSi₂/Sialon

Figure 1 shows a typical optical micrograph of a cross-section of an MoSi₂-40 vol% Sialon composite reinforced with 10 vol% SCS-6 SiC fibre. The central carbon core and outer carbon coating are evident in this figure. EDS and XRD examination in conjunction with SEM showed that the matrix contained mainly MoSi₂, Mo₅Si₃, and β-Si₃N₄ with a small amount of SiC. Since the sample was not etched, the glassy phase [11] which presumably existed between the β-Si₃N₄ grains could not be detected. Furthermore no SiO₂ was observed in the matrix even though the starting MoSi₂ contained a significant amount of this phase. Some may have reacted with carbon from the binder material or carbon die to give the small amount of SiC picked up in the matrix analysis. The remainder may have been consumed in the formation of the glassy phase.

Fig. 1. Optical micrograph of a cross-section of the hot pressed MoSi₂-40 vol% Sialon composite reinforced with 10 vol% SCS-6 SiC fibre.

The addition of low thermal expansion Sialon powder to MoSi₂ was successful in eliminating the formation of cracking in the matrix which was observed in the SCS-6 SiC / MoSi₂ composite investigated previously [10]. This is attributed to the reduction in the coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch between the MoSi₂ matrix and the fibre, resulting from the addition of Sialon powder to MoSi₂.

The C-rich surface coating of the fibre is observed as a ring of black contrast (Fig. 1). This would imply that no severe reaction has occurred between the C-rich surface of the fibre and the matrix during hot pressing cycle. However, closer examination of the interface in cross-section (Fig. 2) reveals penetration of the coating by the bright phase. EDS studies of the bright phase shows that it is Mo₅Si₃. However, removal of the C layer surrounding it suggests that it may have reacted to form Mo₅Si₃C. Since Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy was not available it was not possible to check for C in the Mo₅Si₃ phase. The formation and penetration of the bright phase at the interface could lead to a strong interfacial bond which may have adverse effects on mechanical properties of the composite.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph showing interfacial region in the hot pressed MoSi₂-40 vol% Sialon composite reinforced with 10vol% SCS-6 SiC fibre.

Previous work on creep studies in monolithic and SiC whisker reinforced MoSi₂ [12] has demonstrated that SiO₂ has a detrimental effect on the high temperature strength due to grain boundary sliding of MoSi₂. The absence of SiO₂ in the present composite is therefore likely to have beneficial effect on high temperature mechanical properties. However, the formation and penetration of bright phase at the interface is potentially disadvantageous. Nevertheless, C coating applied to SCS-6 SiC fibre was found to survive hot pressing and should provide at least limited debonding and hence toughening in the matrix.

Microstructure of Al₂O₃ fibre-reinforced MoSi₂

Figure 3 is a typical SEM micrograph showing a cross-section of a hot pressed MoSi₂ matrix composite reinforced with 16 vol% single crystal Al₂O₃ fibres. There is no evidence of any matrix cracking due to high temperature processing of the composite. Figure 4. shows a secondary electron micrograph of the microstructure for the matrix at higher magnification. As seen from Fig. 4 the matrix consisted of three different contrasting phases, light grey, grey, and dark grey. This change in contrast is due to the variation of Mo/Si in these phases. EDS analysis (Table 1) revealed that the light grey and grey phase are Mo₅Si₃ and MoSi₂ respectively whereas the dark phase appears to be glassy SiO₂ with minor fractions of Mo and Al

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of a cross-section of the hot pressed MoSi_2 composite reinforced with 16 vol% single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre.

Fig. 4. SEM micrograph of the microstructure of the matrix of the hot pressed MoSi_2 composite reinforced with 16 vol% single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre.

Table 1. SEM and EDS data from matrix phases in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MoSi}_2$ Composite

Composition (wt%)	Light Grey	Grey	Dark Grey
Si	15.78	36.60	65-90
Mo	85.22	63.30	Trace
Al			Trace

The microstructure of the fibre/matrix interfacial region along with the compositional profile across the interface, analysed by EDS line scan are shown in Figure 5. There is no indication of any reaction at the interface from these composition profiles. The interface was further

investigated by Transmission Electron Microscopy. This investigation reveals (Fig. 6) that a crystalline phase is present at the interface. The phase was identified to be mullite (marked M in Fig. 6) by EDS and Electron Diffraction (ED) studies [see inset- [113] zone axis for mullite]. The mullite composition was found to be variable and lies in the $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 - 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ range.

Fig. 5. SEM micrograph showing the interfacial region and the compositional profile across the interface in the hot pressed MoSi_2 composite reinforced with 16 vol% single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre.

Fig. 6. TEM micrograph of the interfacial region in the hot pressed MoSi_2 composite with 16 vol% single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre. The diffraction pattern (inset) is from the Mullite phase at the interface.

The composite containing 20vol% Al_2O_3 fibre was also examined. It has essentially the same interfacial and microstructure features as the composite containing 16 vol% fibre. As before, the presence of mullite phase was confirmed from TEM and ED observations

The presence of mullite reaction phase at the fibre/matrix interface is likely to influence the mechanical behaviour of the composite. This will, however, depend on the nature of the interfacial bond. The composite will fail in brittle manner if the bond is strong.

Use of various coatings on fibres by different methods has been reported in literature [13] to prevent interfacial reactions and to promote debonding leading to significant enhancement in toughness. The main limitation of this approach is the unavoidable damage suffered by the coating during handling and hot pressing.

Finally it should be noted that thermomechanical stability of a fibre is a major requirement for high temperature structural composites. The SCS-6 SiC and single crystal Al_2O_3 fibres were selected due to their potential for use at high temperatures. The SCS-6 SiC fibres are structurally more stable than Nicalon and Tyranno fibres. However, they suffer from grain growth above 1400°C which reduces their strength. Single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre overcomes this problem of grain growth and retains strength to above 1400°C . The mechanism for the slow strength loss in this fibre may be related to thermal effects on dislocation densities.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions are :

1. This work has demonstrated that the problem of matrix cracking during the processing of SCS-6 SiC/ MoSi_2 may be overcome by the addition of 40 vol% sialon to MoSi_2 , thereby reducing the fibre/matrix overall thermal expansion mismatch. The preservation of C coating (despite local degradation) of the SCS-6 SiC fibre should provide some debonding and pull-out mechanism for enhanced fracture toughness.
2. Single crystal Al_2O_3 fibre-reinforced MoSi_2 composites can be successfully produced without any matrix cracking. This is attributed to good thermal expansion match between the Al_2O_3 fibre and the MoSi_2 matrix.
3. Microstructural and EDS analyses of interfacial regions in SCS-6 SiC reinforced MoSi_2 /Sialon and single crystal Al_2O_3 reinforced MoSi_2 composites have shown the formation of Mo_5Si_3 (or possibly $\text{Mo}_5\text{Si}_3\text{C}$) and mullite phases respectively. Work is underway to identify suitable protective coatings to prevent the formation of such phases at the interface. The objective is to obtain a weak fibre/matrix interface in order to achieve improvements in toughness by fibre debonding and pull-out mechanism.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the technical assistance of Dr.H.S. Ubhi and Dr.P. Korgul in the microscopic and X-ray evaluation.

REFERENCES

1. Meschter, P.J., and Schwartz, D.S., "Silicide-matrix materials for high temperature applications" Journal of Metals, 1989, pp. 52-55.

2. Schlichting, J. "Molybdenum disilicide as a component of modern high temperature composites" (in German), High Temperatures-High Pressures, Vol.10, No.3, 1978, pp. 241-269.
3. Carter, D.H., Petrovic, J.J., Honnell, R.E., and Gibbs, W.S., "SiC-MoSi₂ Composites" Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 10, 1989, pp. 1121-1129.
4. Gibbs, W.S., Petrovic, J.J., and Honnell, R.E., "SiC whisker-MoSi₂ matrix composites", Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 8, 1987, pp. 645-648.
5. Petrovic, J.J., Honnell, R.E., Mitchell, T.E., Wade, R.K., and McClellan, K.J., "Zirconia - Reinforced MoSi₂ Matrix Composites," Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 12, 1991, pp. 1633-1642.
6. Petrovic, J.J., and Honnell, R.E., "SiC Reinforced MoSi₂/WSi₂ Alloy Matrix Composites," Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 11, 1990, pp. 734-744.
7. Xiao, L., and Abbaschian, R., "Microstructure and properties of MoSi₂/Nb interfaces with and without alumina coating", Materials Research Society Symposium, Proceedings, Vol. 239, 1992, pp. 567-573.
8. Fitzer, E., and Remmele, W., Proceedings 5th International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-5, San Diego, CA, TMS-AIME, Warrendale, PA 1985, pp. 515-530.
9. Deve, H.E., Weber, C.H., and Maloney, M., "On the toughness and creep behaviour of fibre reinforced MoSi₂ intermetallic", Materials Science Engineering , Vol. A153, 1992, pp. 668-675.
10. Bhatti, A.R. "Processing and characterisation of monolithic molybdenum disilicide and silicon carbide fibre-reinforced MoSi₂ matrix composites" Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 15, 1994, pp. 1068-1075.
11. Bhatti, A.R., Lewis, M.H., Lumby, R.J., and North, B. "The microstructure of sintered Si-Al-O-N ceramics", Journal of Materials Science, Vol.15, 1980, pp.103-113.
12. Sadananda, K., Jones, K., Feng, J., Petrovic, J.J., and Vasudevan, A.K., "Creep of monolithic and SiC-whisker reinforced MoSi₂", Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings, Vol. 12, 1991, pp. 1671-1678.
13. Lu, T.C., Deng, Y.G., Levi, C.G., and Mehrabian, R., "On the strength and stiffness of ductile phase reinforced MoSi₂ Composites for elevated temperatures", Proceedings. Conference, ASM, Cincinnati, OH, 1991.